

The Mediating Role of Career Satisfaction in the Impact of Person-Organization Fit on Cyberloafing

Kişi-Örgüt Uyumunun Sanal Kaytarmaya Etkisinde Kariyer Tatmininin Aracı Rolü

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Abstract

As well as the facilitating impacts of technological developments in the globalizing world on human life, it is seen that they also provide sociological, psychological, cultural and behavioral changes. This new change in social and cultural life has revealed behavioral innovations in daily habits. Perhaps the most important of these behaviors is the bond established with social media and living within the axis of this bond. This new change in social life has affected daily habits. The new habits that people acquire also bring about different behavioral changes in working life. Examining the impacts of these changes has opened a new field for researchers. In this context, the present study aimed to investigate the mediating role of career satisfaction in the impact of person-organization fit on cyberloafing. To this end, a quantitative study based on the survey technique was conducted with employees and managers of manufacturing enterprises operating in Kayseri Organized Industrial Zone. According to the data obtained from the surveys from 430 manufacturing sector employees and managers, it was concluded that person-organization fit has a negative impact on cyberloafing, a positive impact on career satisfaction, and career satisfaction has a negative impact on cyberloafing. Also, it was found that career satisfaction mediates the insignificant relationship between person-organization fit and cyberloafing.

Keywords: Person-Organization Fit, Career Satisfaction, Cyberloafing.

JEL Codes: M10,M19,C12

Özet

Globalleşen dünyadaki teknolojik gelişmeler insan hayatındaki kolaylaştırıcı etkilerinin yanı sıra, sosyolojik, psikolojik, kültürel ve davranışsal olarak değişmesini sağladığı görülmektedir. Sosyal ve kültürel hayatta başlayan bu yeni değişim, gündelik alışkanlıklarda davranışsal yenilikler ortaya çıkarmıştır. Bu davranışların belki de en önemlisi sosyal medya ile kurulan bağ ve bu bağ ekseninde yaşamalarıdır. Sosyal hayatta başlayan bu yeni değişim, gündelik alışkanlıkları etkilemiştir. İnsanların edindiği yeni alışkanlıklar, çalışma hayatında da farklı davranışsal değişimleri beraberinde getirmiştir. Bu değişimlerin etkilerini incelemek araştırmacılar açısından yeni bir alan açmıştır. Bu bağlamda çalışmada kişi-örgüt uyumunun sanal kaytarmaya etkisinde kariyer tatmininin aracı rolü araştırılmak istenmiştir. Bu amaçla, Kayseri Organize Sanayi Bölgesi'nde faaliyet gösteren imalat işletmelerinin çalışanları ve yöneticileri ile anket tekniğine dayalı nicel bir araştırma yapılmıştır. 430 imalat sektörü çalışan ve yöneticisinden elde edilen anketler ile elde edilen verilere göre, kişi-örgüt uyumunun sanal kaytarma üzerinde negatif, kariyer tatmini üzerinde pozitif etkiye sahip olduğu ve kariyer tatmininin sanal kaytarma üzerinde negatif etkiye sahip olduğu sonucuna varılmıştır. Ayrıca, kariyer tatmininin kişi-örgüt uyumu ile önemsiz sanal kaytarma ilişkisine aracılık ettiği belirlenmiştir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Kişi-Örgüt Uyumunu, Kariyer Tatmini, Sanal Kaytarma.

JEL Kodları: M10,M19,C12

Introduction

The individual-organization fit of employees is a subject examined by researchers from many perspectives. Individuals with a high level of fit with the organization they work for show high performance (Sezgin, 2006: 560; Aktaş, 2011: 18; Raddatz, 2024: 2; Park & Hai, 2024:853). The examination of cyberloafing behavior, which has emerged as one of the significant factors in the decrease of individual-organization fit in recent years, is significant in terms of determining it as a factor that reduces employee performance and workplace efficiency (Henle, Kohut, & Booth, 2009: 904; Hessari, et al., 2024).

In general, cyberloafing includes using computer and internet systems, which are provided for business purposes, for personal purposes as well as using personal electronic devices during the time that must be spent on work at the workplace (Örücü & Yıldız, 2014: 99; Nweke, Jarrar & Horoub, 2024: 3). It is possible to access almost in every environment because of reasons e.g., the speed of technological developments, widespread use of the internet, its cheapness and easy availability (Wallace, 2004: 5; Krishna & Agrawal, 2023: 649).

The manufacturing sector covers the manufacturing with light or heavy industry machinery. For this reason, manufacturing sites are places where occupational safety and employee health, occupational accidents, fatal injuries, and accidents that might damage the workplace are likely to occur. A momentary inattention might cause injuries, fatal accidents, or fires. For this reason, employees need to perform their work with due care during work at the workplace. An innocent cyberloafing behavior that is not insignificant might cause irreparable or very costly outcomes. Based on this, the present study focused on the results of cyberloafing behavior in the manufacturing sector.

Career is associated with where people want to see themselves in business life. Career satisfaction is the level of satisfaction of individuals with their current career positions (Tahiry & Ekmekcioglu, 2023: 293; Granek et al., 2024: 214). Although individuals who have high career satisfaction focus on the better, those with low career satisfaction cause them to develop actions that reduce their own and others' performance.

Low individual-organization fit and high cyberloafing are two undesirable situations in a workplace. It is considered that career satisfaction will have a mediating role in controlling these two undesirable situations in an organization. For this reason, in the present study, career satisfaction was discussed as a mediating variable in the relationship between cyberloafing and individual-organization fit.

Based on the importance of the subject explained above, the study aimed to uncover the impact of

cyberloafing in the workplace on individual-organization fit and the role of career satisfaction in this relationship. In line with this purpose, the conceptual framework, study model, and hypotheses are included in the first part of the present study.

Quantitative study methods were used to conduct a survey on employees and managers in manufacturing businesses located in Kayseri Organized Industrial Zone. According to the analysis of the data obtained in the quantitative stage, it was concluded that cyberloafing reduces person-organization fit and that career satisfaction mediated the relationship between person-organization fit and cyberloafing. The present study is original in that it examines person-organization fit, cyberloafing and career satisfaction together. In the conclusion of the present study, suggestions for future studies were made in the light of the evaluation of the results obtained.

Conceptual Framework/Theory

The concept of person-organization fit emerges in today's business world as a significant step, especially in the recruitment processes and as a factor that increases employee performance. Previous studies show that in organizations where person-organization fit is high, employees are problem solvers, participants in organizational activities, open to helping other workmates, willing to take on additional tasks and responsibilities to achieve organizational goals, and thus, employees show high performance (Chatman, 1991: 465; Kristof-Brown, Zimmerman, & Johnson, 2005: 283; Kristof-Brown, 2000: 651; Tsui, Pearce, Porter, & Tripoli, 1997: 1095; Kooij, Tims, & Akkermans, 2017: 9; Sezgin, 2006: 560; Loi, Hang-Yoe, & Folay, 2006: 108; Aktaş, 2011: 18; Menter, Göcke & Zeeb, 2024:930; Wuryaningrat et al., 2024:161; Jufrizen et al.,2024:360; Iqbal & Piwowar-Sulej, 2024: 301).

When the person-organization fit reaches a high level, in other words, when these actors have similar basic characteristics and meet each other's expectations and needs, the maximum benefit might be achieved, but high fit also has some disadvantages (O'Reilly et al., 1991: 492). To illustrate, according to Bakker & Demerouti (2007), high fit contains some risks over time and might create organization members who think and act in the same way over time. As a natural result of this, an organization closed to proactive and innovative thoughts might inevitably emerge (Bakker & Demerouti, 2017: 283; Raddatz, 2024: 13). Also, for employees with difficulty adapting themselves to the organization, this might cause them to show performance-reducing behaviors (Milliken, Morrison, & Hewlin, 2003: 1460; Vakola & Bouradas, 2005: 450).

Career, which is widely researched in the literature with many different definitions, is, in summary, the

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combination of the knowledge and experience a person has gained throughout their life. Career satisfaction, on the other hand, is the subjective evaluation of a person's success (Colakoglu, 2011: 50; Kong, Cheung & Song, 2012: 79). In other words, it is the positive expectations and perceptions of employees that they will achieve their future career targets associated with their jobs (Nauta, et al., 2009: 236; Yüksel, 2005: 304). Previous studies show that career satisfaction occurs when individuals are in an organization with values parallel to their own and employees are happy with all their experiences (Erdogan, Kraimer, & Liden, 2004: 307; Gürlek, 2020: 261). Employees who do not have career satisfaction or have low satisfaction levels might show negative behaviors towards the company, their performance might decrease, and might negatively affect the performance of other employees (McGinley, 2009: 12).

Despite the developing technology, one of the most significant resources in organizations is the human factor. Although the widespread use of the internet, the existence of automation systems, and the mechanization brought by technological developments reduce the workload of employees, a diversification in job requirements emerges in parallel with this new technology (Çivilidağ, 2017: 356). As the trade network in the globalizing world is based on the internet infrastructure, it provides significant contributions e.g., the establishment of cost-reducing, fast, and efficient communication networks, and the establishment of global communication and marketing networks (Liberman, Seidman, MC & Buffardğ, 2011: 2192). The necessity of intensive internet use in workplaces has become a situation that allows employees to spend their free time in a world that contains information outside of work. This is described as cyberloafing and is addressed in two categories significant cyberloafing and insignificant cyberloafing (Blanchard & Henle, 2008: 1071; Henle, Kohut, & Booth, 2009: 909; Örucü & Yıldız, 2014: 110).

Significant cyberloafing is the attitude of employees who spend time on the internet by using the technological infrastructure and consumables of the workplace for matters other than work, which allows the workplace to deliberately cause production, time, and cost losses (Ünal & Tekdemir, 2015: 95; Kaplan & Öğüt, 2012: 10; Lim, 2002: 687). Although employees use their personal mobile technologies during working hours, they are interpreted as cyberloafing because they perform this action during working hours (Keklik, Kılıç, Yıldız & Yıldız, 2015: 130; Çiçek, 2020: 199). Also, actions e.g., playing games, spending time on sites that adults might access, surfing on topics unassociated with work, and online gambling are considered serious loafing (Blanchard & Henle, 2008: 1068).

However, the attention span of a medically normal individual is 20 minutes (Dukette & Cornish, 2009:

72). Expecting an employee to focus on their work for 8-10 hours without taking a break from the start of the shift is not in line with human nature. Employees need time to relax, shop, and surf the internet for no reason at all in the workplace. They might use this time for entertainment purposes unassociated with their work (Özkalp, Aydın & Tekeli, 2012: 21). The momentary loafing behaviors that employees have, e.g., using social media, surfing the internet, and sending e-mails regarding their matters, enable them to be more productive than in the past, cope with the stress they face more easily, and increase job satisfaction (Askew, et al., 2014: 515; Kaplan & Çetinkaya, 2014: 30; Andreassen, Torheseim & Pallesen, 2014: 913; Lim & Teo, 2024: 443).

When the literature was reviewed, it was found that significant cyberloafing has negative impacts on the integration of person-organization fit and unproductive behaviors emerge (Liberman, Seidman, MC & Buffardğ, 2011: 2192; Mea, 2024: 28; Lim, 2002: 687; Dabney, 1995: 315). On the other hand, since it was found that insignificant cyberloafing has a productivity-enhancing impact (Andreassen, Torheseim & Pallesen, 2014: 913; Örucü & Yıldız, 2014: 113), it is considered that it will have positive impacts on employee-organization fit. Increasing levels of person-organization fit have increasing impacts on career satisfaction (Gürlek, 2020: 260; Akkan, 2022: 43; Park & Hai, 2024: 852).

According to the above explanations and study results, it might be speculated that career satisfaction will have a mediating role in the impact of person-organization fit on cyberloafing. In this context, the main purpose of the present study is to determine the impact of person-organization fit on cyberloafing and the mediating role of career satisfaction between the variables. The hypotheses and study model created in this framework are as follows.

Figure 1. Research Model

H1: Person-organization fit has a negative impact on cyberloafing

H2: Person-organization fit has a negative impact on minor cyberloafing.

H3: Person-organization fit has a positive impact on career satisfaction.

H4: Career satisfaction has a negative impact on significant cyberloafing.

H5: Career satisfaction has a negative impact on frivolous cyberloafing.

H6: Career satisfaction has a mediating impact on the relationship between person-organization fit and cyberloafing.

H7: Career satisfaction has a mediating impact on the relationship between person-organization fit and insignificant cyberloafing.

Method

The study was conducted to test hypotheses developed based on literature data. The present study method was quantitative. The data were collected through face-to-face surveys and were analyzed using the Structural Equation Modeling, which was preferred because it is a powerful method in that it might test multiple variables together (Russell, Kahn & Altmaier, 1998: 18) and might produce more effective results in mediation analysis (Little, Card, Bovaird, Preacher & Crandall, 2007: 212). In the analysis of the data, the SPSS v24 package program was used to determine pretests and descriptive statistics, and IBM AMOS v24 package program was used for SEM and CFA analyses.

Population-Sample

The population of the present study consisted of employees and managers of manufacturing enterprises operating in Kayseri Organized Industrial Zone. The sampling method of the present study was Convenience Sampling. The reason for choosing this method is that it is an improbable method and offers advantages e.g., geographical proximity, accessibility at a certain time and voluntary participation (Etikan, Musa, & Alkassim, 2016). According to the data of Kayseri Governorship, the number of employees in Organized Industrial Zone is 70000 (kayseri.gov.tr, 2024). The sample size was calculated as 394 with a 5% error margin using the power analysis method suggested by Kadam and Bhalerao (2010) (Kadam & Bhalerao, 2010). Since 430 people participated in this study, it was concluded that the sample size was sufficient. Information about the participants is shared in the table below.

Table 1. Participant Information

		Number	Percentage
Gender	Female	218	50.7%
	Male	212	49.3%
Marital status	Married	345	80.2%
	Single	85	19.8%

Title	Employee	286	66.5%
	Executive	144	33.5%
Total Working Hours	Less than 1 Year	38	8.8%
	1 Year – 5 Years	76	17.7%
	6 Years – 10 Years	91	21.2%
	11 Years – 15 Years	70	16.3%
	16 Years – 20 Years	85	19.8%
	More Than 21 Years	70	16.3%
Age Information	18 – 25 Years Old	127	29.5%
	26 – 35 Years Old	210	48.8%
	36 – 45 Years Old	80	18.6%
	46 – 55 Years Old	13	3.1%
Educational Status	Literate	3	0.7%
	Primary education	21	4.9%
	High school	330	76.7%
	Associate Degree	66	15.3%
	University	10	2.3%

Scales

Person-Organization Fit Scale: This single-dimension, four-item scale developed by Netemeyer et al. (1987) was used (Netemeyer, Boles, O. & McMurrian, 1987: 95). Sample scale items were "I think my values match well with my workplace" and "My workplace has the same values as me regarding honesty".

Career Satisfaction Scale: The single-dimension, five-item scale developed by Greenhaus et al. (1990) was used in the study (Greenhaus, Parasuraman & Wormley, 1990: 72). Sample scale items were "I am satisfied with the success I have achieved in my career" and "I am satisfied with the progress I have made towards achieving my career development goals".

Cyberloafing Scale: The scale consisting of two dimensions called significant cyberloafing activities and insignificant cyberloafing activities developed by Örücü and Yıldız (2014) was used in the study (Örücü & Yıldız, 2014: 113). The significant cyberloafing activities dimension of the scale consists of 8 items, and the insignificant cyberloafing activities dimension consists of 6 items. Sample scale items are "Downloading music, videos, movies or documents from the Internet" and "Receiving, sending or checking e-mail for non-work-related communication". The scale items consisted of 7 Likert-style statements (1-Strongly Disagree, 7-Strongly Agree).

Analysis of Data

A two-stage approach was followed for the analysis of the data (Anderson & Gerbing, 1992: 322). In this

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context, firstly the prerequisites of the data e.g., factor analysis and common method variance analysis were examined. Before proceeding to this stage, the distribution normality of the data was checked and their suitability for the SEM approach was determined. To this end, skewness and kurtosis values were examined and it was seen that they were between -1.5 and +1.5. Based on these results, it was concluded that the distribution was normal (Bai & Ng, 2005: 51; Tabachnick & Fidell, 2007: 80-81). Harman's "Single Factor Test" approach was applied for the

common method variance error. Thus, since the variance value formed when all variables were forced to a single factor distribution was determined to be 29%, it was concluded that there was no common method variance error (Harman, 1976: 11). Then, confirmatory factor analysis was performed. A basic four-factor model and three alternative models were developed and the Chi-Square differences were tested to see which model fit the data better (Anderson & Gerbing, 1988: 421) (Anderson & Gerbing, 1988).

Table 2. Factor Analysis Results

Model	Factor	χ^2	df	$\Delta \chi^2$	RMSEA	IFI	TL	CFI
Main Model	4-Factor Research Model	544.16	229		0.078	0.941	0.944	0.938
Model 1	3-Factor Model: Major and minor cyberloafing are grouped under one factor	796.32	241	252.16 p=0.00	0.096	0.886	0.884	0.880
Model 2	2-Factor Model: Major and minor cyberloafing and career satisfaction are grouped under one factor	932.61	241	388.45 p=0.00	0.112	0.861	0.880	0.842
Model 3	Single-Factor Model: All variables are gathered under a single factor.	1586.1	243	1041.94 p=0.00	0.144	0.735	0.744	0.710

As given in Table 2, the four-factor main model has the best goodness of fit values ($\chi^2 / df = 2.736$, IFI = 0.941, TLI = 0.944, CFI = 0.938, RMSEA = 0.078). These results showed that the main model has good discriminant validity results (Hinkin, 1998: 105; Steiger, 1990: 175). To further test the discriminant validity, the steps suggested by Netemeyer et al. (1990) were followed. In this context, the square root of the variance (AVE) generated from the variables must

exceed the correlation coefficient between the variables. Also, for convergent validity, variance and factor values (AVE) and Composite Reliability (CR) coefficients were calculated and tested to find out whether they were within the accepted values (AVE = 0.50; Factor loading = 0.50; CR = 0.70) (Fornell & Larcker, 1981: 41). The results are shared in Tables 3 and 4.

Table 3. Factor Analysis Results

Variables	Items	Factor Loading	CR	AVE	Alpha
Person-Organization Fit	POF1	0.811	0.811	0.519	0.818
	POF2	0.716			
	POF3	0.654			
	POF4	0.691			

Career Satisfaction	CS1	0.763	0.834	0.504	0.832
	CS2	0.781			
	CS3	0.632			
	CS4	0.625			
	CS5	0.733			
Significant Cyberloafing Activities	SIGNIFICANTCA1	0.750	0.907	0.551	0.912
	SIGNIFICANTCA2	0.788			
	SIGNIFICANTCA3	0.698			
	SIGNIFICANTCA4	0.646			
	SIGNIFICANTCA5	0.778			
	SIGNIFICANTCA6	0.824			
	SIGNIFICANTCA7	0.708			
	SIGNIFICANTCA8	0.731			
Insignificant Cyberloafing Activities	INSIGNIFICANTCA1	0.607	0.857	0.507	0.860
	INSIGNIFICANTCA2	0.775			
	INSIGNIFICANTCA3	0.603			
	INSIGNIFICANTCA4	0.544			
	INSIGNIFICANTCA5	0.793			
	INSIGNIFICANTCA6	0.886			

As given in the table, all values meet the convergent validity criterion. Correlations between variables and other descriptive information are given in Table 4.

Table 4. Correlation Analysis Results

Scales	Standard Deviation	Mean	1	2	3	4
1. Person Organization Compliance	0.986	2.871	(0.720)			
2. Career Satisfaction	1.112	2.932	0.311**	(0.710)		
3. Significant Cyberloafing	1.205	3.954	-0.344**	-0.232**	(0.742)	
4. Insignificant Cyberloafing	1.186	3.651	-0.186*	-0.301**	0.456***	(0.712)
*p<0.05; **p < 0.01; ***p<0.001						

The correlation coefficients between the variables were significant and the square root of the variance values exceeded the correlation coefficients. When all of these results were examined together, it was concluded that the present study met all the criteria of convergent and discriminant validity, showed a

normal distribution, and there was no common method variance error in the present study. Thus, it was seen that the data showed successful results in the first step of the two-stage approach suggested by Anderson and Gerbing (1992) (Anderson & Gerbing, 1992: 322).

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Hypothesis Tests

In the second phase of the present study, which was hypothesis testing, the SEM approach was adopted and the goodness of fit values of the model established with the IBM AMOS v24 program are as follows: $\chi^2/df = 2.908$, $IFI = 0.904$, $TLI = 0.898$, $CFI = 0.911$, $RMSEA = 0.078$. These results showed that the main model had a good level of goodness of fit results (Hinkin, 1998: 112; Steiger, 1990: 178). The results obtained from the analysis are in the table below.

Table 5. Hypothesis Analysis Results

Path Analysis	β	Critical Ratio	R2
Person-organization fit →Significant Cyberloafing	-0.281***	-6,144	0,32
Person-organization fit →Insignificant Cyberloafing	-0.144*	-4,906	0,18
Person-organization fit →Career Satisfaction	0.348***	8,169	0,14
Career Satisfaction → Significant Cyberloafing	-0.186**	-5,141	0,32
Career Satisfaction →Insignificant Cyberloafing	-0.282***	-6,148	0,18

*** $p < 0.001$; ** $p < 0.01$; * $p < 0.05$

As a result of the analysis, it was found that person-organization fit affected significant cyberloafing activities significantly and negatively ($\beta = -0.281$; $p < 0.001$) along with insignificant cyberloafing activities ($\beta = -0.144$; $p < 0.05$). Besides person-organization fit affected career satisfaction significantly and positively ($\beta = 0.348$; $p < 0.001$). Also, career satisfaction significantly and negatively affected significant cyberloafing activities ($\beta = -0.186$; $p < 0.01$); insignificant cyberloafing activities ($\beta = -0.282$; $p < 0.001$).

According to Hair et al. (2010: 156) r^2 values below 0.25 indicate a weak accuracy, below 0.50 indicate a moderate accuracy, and below 0.75 show a substantial predictive accuracy. When the R^2 values were examined, it was determined that this value was respectively 0.32, 0.18 and 0.14 for the variables of sig-

nificant cyberloafing, insignificant cyberloafing and career satisfaction.

The bootstrapping method was used to determine the mediating impact in the present study. The mediating impact results obtained with this method are given in the table below.

Table 6. Results of Mediation Analysis

Path Analysis	Direct Impact	Indirect Impact	Total Impact
Person-organization fit →Career satisfaction →Significant Cyberloafing	-0.281***	-0.065	0.346***
Person-organization fit →Career satisfaction →Insignificant Cyberloafing	-0.144*	-0.098**	-0.242**

*** $p < 0.001$; * $p < 0.05$; Bootstrapping sample = 2000

As given in Table 6, in the analysis conducted with the bootstrapping method, the indirect impact parameter was insignificant for the "Person-organization fit →Career satisfaction →Significant Cyberloafing" ($\beta = -0.065$; $p > 0.05$), and was significant for the path "Person-organization fit →Career satisfaction →Insignificant Cyberloafing" ($\beta = -0.098$; $p < 0.01$). Based on this result, it was concluded that career satisfaction mediates the relationship between person-organization fit and insignificant cyberloafing activities. The results of the hypothesis tests are given in the table below.

Table 7. Hypothesis Results

Hypothesis	Conclusion
H1: Person-organization fit has a negative impact on cyberloafing	Accepted
H2: Person-organization fit has a negative impact on minor cyberloafing.	Accepted
H3: Person-organization fit has a positive impact on career satisfaction.	Accepted
H4: Career satisfaction has a negative impact on significant cyberloafing.	Accepted

H5: Career satisfaction has a negative impact on frivolous cyberloafing.	Accepted
H6: Career satisfaction has a mediating impact on the relationship between person-organization fit and cyberloafing.	Rejected
H7: Career satisfaction has a mediating impact on the relationship between person-organization fit and insignificant cyberloafing.	Accepted

Conclusion

Recent studies report that cyberloafing has a detrimental impact on person-organization fit (Kerse, Soyalin & Karabey, 2016; Lim & Chen, 2012: 350; Özkalp, Aydın & Tekeli, 2012: 21). The present study aimed to uncover the mediating role of career satisfaction in the impact of cyberloafing on person-organization fit. To this end, a quantitative study was conducted to test the hypotheses created through a literature review. A face-to-face survey was conducted with managers and employees of the manufacturing sector in Kayseri province to collect data for the present study.

According to the results of the relationships tested with the Structural Equation Modeling Approach, it was found that cyberloafing negative impacts on individual-organization fit. In other words, employees who commit cyberloafing at work lose their harmony with the organization and resort to using their own mobile devices or computer and internet services provided by businesses for business purposes in non-work activities. Of course, it is useful to emphasize that this is divided into two significant and insignificant cyberloafing. According to the results of the present study, it was found that person-organization fit has negative impact on significant and insignificant cyberloafing. This finding of the present study is similar to the studies of Koay (2018), Gowrisankar and Vimala (2019) and Çiçek (2020). This situation is important as it shows that shirking is not a positive concept by no means.

According to another finding of the present study, it was found that person-organization fit has a positive impact on career satisfaction. The main reason for this might be the fact that a large part of the elements in Maslow's pyramid of needs (being oneself, dignity, physical needs, love) are provided by career satisfaction (Maslow, 1954: 92). This finding of the present study is similar to the studies of Akkan (2022), Gürlek (2020), Demirdelen & Ulama (2013) and McGinley (2009). Employees with high levels of satisfaction can be expected to exhibit work dedication, organizational citizenship, and other positive organizational behaviors.

Another finding of the present study is that career satisfaction has negative impacts on cyberloafing. Employees with high career satisfaction make significant contributions to business performance (Spurk, Abele, & Volmer, 2011: 316). The most significant outcomes of career satisfaction for organizations are organizational commitment, job satisfaction, increased psychological well-being in employees, and high performance (Çiçek, 2020: 210; Martin & Cullen, 2006: 177). Naturally, employees who are compatible with their workplace and have high career satisfaction levels are expected to avoid non-work, dysfunctional, and negative behaviors. For this reason, it is normal for cyberloafing and similar negative behaviors to decrease in workplaces where individuals have high career satisfaction.

The results of the mediating variable analysis showed that career satisfaction mediates the relationship between person-organization fit and insignificant cyberloafing. In other words, high individual-organization level and career satisfaction prevent cyberloafing. Based on this, it was concluded that "to have workplace efficiency, high-performance work of employees, employees who are in harmony with the workplace and have high career satisfaction, it is significant to take measures to control cyberloafing". As a result of the present study, the following suggestions are made.

- Employees who work in manufacturing businesses have to work more carefully than employees who work in other businesses. The slightest carelessness or negligence might cause irreparable outcomes. According to TURKSTAT data, in the last 3 months of 2024, the internet access rate of employees working as salaried or daily wage earners and managers was over 99% (TUIK, 2024), and according to ISIG Labor Assembly data, 878 employees lost their lives in the first 6 months of the year (ISIG, 2024). In light of this, it is recommended that measures be taken and rules be set to prevent cyberloafing, especially in manufacturing businesses.
- Instead of evaluating cyberloafing activities as manageable activities and immediately punishing them, the underlying reasons must be investigated. Another suggestion is to perform activities that increase the harmony between the individual and the organization of the employees and projects that strengthen the communication and bond between the superior and the subordinate.
- Since career satisfaction is a subjective assessment of individuals, for them to be in the place they have determined in their career plans, it is necessary to have a suitable organizational setting, to provide equal opportunities, to take into account organizational justice, and to operate mechanisms that help employees achieve their career goals. The belief that an employee who does his/her job well will get a good job will prevent the employee from

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either virtual or actual loafing.

- New performance-based payment tools might be developed in manufacturing businesses. It is considered that the reward system will prevent cyberloafing.

The present study had some limitations. Firstly, it must be noted that there was a limitation in terms of generalization. The main reason for this is that the present study was conducted in one city. Also, it must be taken into account that employees might be subjective when answering variables e.g., cyberloafing, person-organization fit and career satisfaction. Finally, it is considered that the fact that the survey data were collected from all employees at the same time might cause common method variance errors.

The present study is original because it investigated the variables of cyberloafing, person-organization fit and career satisfaction together and in the manufacturing sector. It might be speculated that the present study findings are significant in terms of guiding the activities of the manufacturing sector in particular and all businesses in general. For this reason, it is expected that the present study will contribute to the relevant literature. Also, suggestions are made for future studies. In this context, it is recommended that future studies examine the impacts of cyberloafing on person-organization fit and test ethical leadership as a mediating variable.

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